

Supplementary Figure S2. Specificity test of F-2 monoclonal antibody in the recognition of STAT3 protein. **(A)** Immunofluorescence staining data showed a specific STAT3 signal in the cell cytoplasm and nucleus of A549 cell was recognized by the F-2 antibody compared with a donkey anti-mouse 2oAb (Alexa546; 1/50 dilution) alone group. Nucleus DNA was stained with DAPI to define nuclear localization. Scale bar = 20 μ m. **(B)** Western blot analysis of F-2 monoclonal antibody specificity for STAT3 protein identification using NIH/3T3 mouse embryonic fibroblast cells. (Left panel) The specific signal of STAT3 recognized by F-2 antibody (1/250 dilution) in Western blot analysis of NIH/3T3 cells. (Right panel) The Stat3 Western blot image is from commercial data sheet for F-2 antibody quality control.